

Diamond Mines and Exploring Methods of Diamonds in Andhradesa

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ABSTRACT

The diamonds are available in all parts of the world but very a smaller in amount. When European traveler visited India in general and Andradesa particular mentioned the names of diamond mines and process was given in their accounts in detail. In this backdrop the present through light on the diamond mines in Andhradesa, type of searching for diamonds, caste names were used based on the quality of diamonds, cutting system, and destructive mode of mining in the agricultural fields. An important paper was written by Trans Phil in 1677 A.D and referred Golconda had twenty three mines. They were in the alluvium of the river Krishna and others in the vicinity of Cuddapah and Karnool both localities being in the territories of the Kingdom of Mutfli, Golconda kingdom, Carnatic Rajas of Vijayanagar and later under the reign of Nawabs of Bijapur. ‘Diamond mining in this part of the country may be of great antiquity’.

The travellers stated that natives used three types of searching methods for diamonds. Gani- Kollur, Gollapalle, Mallavilli, Rajpet, Codavetty kallu, Damarapad and Malawaram mines are situated in Coastal Andhra Candapetta, Currapully, Banganapalle and Vajra Karur mines are in the Ceded districts. Therefore the farmers were strongly opposed to the extension of the diamond mines because the plenty of cultivating ground went on vain.

Key Words: Diamond mining, Traveler, Cultivating ground, Andradesa,

Introduction

The diamonds are the most precious of all stones and it is the most valuable commercial article of trade. Naturally searching for diamonds is the most awaited or difficult job, while searching for diamonds sometimes it may success and sometimes it may vain the hard work. The diamonds are available in all parts of the world but very a smaller in amount. When European traveller visited India in general and Andradesa particular mentioned the names of diamond mines and process was given in their accounts in detail. In this backdrop the present through light on the diamond mines in Andhradesa, type of searching for diamonds, caste names were used based on the quality of diamonds, cutting system, and destructive mode of mining in the agricultural fields.

The mines area situated in Coastal Andhra and Rayalaseema regions of former Andhradesa. Here the diamond mines were very common, some of the mines so famous under the name of Golconda. An important paper was written by Trans Phil in 1677 A.D and referred Golconda had twenty three mines. They were in the alluvium of the river Krishna and others in the vicinity of Cuddapah and Karnool both localities being in the territories of the Kingdom of Mutfli, Golconda kingdom, Carnatic Rajas of Vijayanagar and later under the reign of Nawabs of Bijapur. 'Diamond mining in this part of the country may be of great antiquity'. The world famous Koh-i-noor diamond was found from the Krishna river region.¹ Hyene informed that he visited five different diamond mines in peninsula India and examined the nature of the strata in which the precious stones were found.²

Searching for Diamonds

Marco Polo mentioned this as the Kingdom of Mutfli where he saw three ways of searching diamonds by the natives. First one he described that when the heavy winter rains fell in lofty mountains the fast-moving waters came down from the mountains. When the rains over the speed of water ceased, then they were searching the ground of the region and found number of diamonds. There were plenty to be found in summer also but due heavy heat and scarcity of water no one to dare for searching diamonds.³ The second way he mentioned that among these mountains great and deep valleys which was difficult to access the bottom beside that the

widespread of venomous serpents and other vermin was danger to collect the diamonds. There the number of white eagles started hunting in the mountains for serpents. The men who looked for diamonds took some pieces of flesh threw over the valley then eagles pounced upon the meat and carried it up to some rocky hill-top where the men were awaiting and made loud sound to drive them away. The pieces of meat was collected by the men and found them full of diamonds which had stuck to the meat down in the bottom of valley. The third way was, the white eagles nests was searched by men who found in their excrements plenty of diamonds which the birds swallowed in consuming the meat that was spread into the valleys and some diamonds found in their stomachs.⁴

Gani- Kollur diamond mine

The earliest trustworthy account about these diamond mines was Tavernier who made journey and especially purchased diamonds from Gani- Kollur which was in the south of Pulichinta and west of Bellam Konda. It was the most important amongst all mines in the Telugu land.⁵ Thevenot mentioned Kollur name as *Gani*.⁶ But Tavernier wrote that this place was “called in Persian *Coulour* and *Gani* in Indian languages.⁷ The word *Gani* is equivalent to the Persian Kan-i, signifying ‘mine of’ where precious stones and minerals were available. It had been referred to connect with other mines. The *Economic Geology of India* was fully discussed its location on the river Krishna and routes to reach besides that Tavernier also mentioned the same in his accounts.⁸ About Kollur diamond mine Methwold stated that ‘first of diamonds lately discovered in this kingdom’ but most men said that it was an accident to discover.⁹ Tavernier appended that “it is only about 100 years since this mine was discovered when a poor man, digging a piece of ground where he purposed to sow millet, found a pointe naïve weighing nearly 25 carats”. The rumor of this new discovery quickly spread all over the country some wealthy persons began to the mine place where they found large stones in large quantity than in any other mines.¹⁰ It was twelve gentu leagues equal to one hundred eight English miles distant from Masulipatam. Daily thirty thousand men worked in that mine. Some were digging and filling the dust in baskets. Few people were carrying the earth up to a square level place where they washed out water with buckets and widened it four or five inches in thickness which was dried in the sunshine. The next day some of them gathered the great stones with their hands the

rest was thrown out. ‘They find the diamonds amongst the dust and sometimes none’.¹¹ Tavernier stated that Kollur was important mine because of the number of large stones were found there. But the Colour of diamonds was a misfortunate that the stones were not clear and that their water contained indications of the quality of the soil where they were found. If the soil was wet and humid the stones inclined to blackness; if it was reddish tended to red and so with other conditions sometimes towards green and yellow as there was multifariousness of soil, the area of town and mountain. He also notified that for the examination of stones whether which contained the water and flaws, Indians done this job at night whereas in Europe at daylight.¹²

Gollapalle, Mallavilli and Rajpet mines

Streynsham Master informed that Gollapalle mine which was in the Nuzvid territory, twenty five miles north-east of Vijayawada and thirteen and half miles from Eluru (West Godavari district). It was part of Golconda mines. Some of his persons invested money for diamonds here several most eminent merchants approached them at Gollapalle. He directly eye-witnessed that the manner of diamond mining. Next digging the gravel earth which was washed away melted like sugar and ran out of holes with the water, so the gravel and all diamonds remained. Per month one and half pagodas were paid to the miners and those labourers who worked in the mines.¹³ Mallavilli was another diamond mine five miles away from Gollapalle mine both were in full working during his visit in 1679. Next he reached to Rajpet mine which was near to Mallavilli where forty thousand miners worked.¹⁴ Hyene informed that he first visited diamond mine Mallavilli village sixteen miles west south-west of Eluru, in this district seven villages had diamond mines including Mallavilli. The names of the other six villages were Ganipartala or Partal, Atkur, Burthenpadu, Pertalla, Wustapilly and Codavettykallu. So it would be appeared that the gem was scattered over a considerable extent in this part of the country. Earlier they owned by a zamindar Opparow (maybe Appa Rao) later which had taken and managed by the Nizam. He further recounted that the English East India Company got possession of this circar but these villages were retained by the Nizam.¹⁵

Codavetty kallu mine

Hyene apprised that the traditional story of the discovery of the diamond mine at Codavetty kallu was one of the seven villages. One day a shepherd found some useful stones

which appeared to him near narrow valley hence he collected many and utilized them. Unfortunately he used them to ‘a light of kindle his tobacco’ at the residence of zamindar Opparow. The stones had been observed by the servant of zamindar, who knew the value and made inquiry how the shepherd had obtained it. The man revealed all that he knew besides his wife and children were also examined. At last zamindar knew that they were ignorant and then the mine was taken care. ‘It was said bullock loads of diamonds were found near that nullah, until at length the Nizam’ later he apprised of the discovery and took over the diamond mine by Nizam.¹⁶

Damarapad and Malawaram mines

Tavernier explained about some other mines near Damarapad and Malawaram on the Krishna were located between Kollur and Rammalakota. He told that these were found about thirty or forty years ago but the King orders mines were closed because fraud allegations against them. Here stones had green crust, beautiful, transparent and even more beautiful than the others but when tried to grind them cut into pieces.¹⁷ When Hyene passed through a village Chennur about twenty miles north from Nellore he was informed that diamond mines existed in its vicinity and that not many years ago beside diamonds had been found the first water which the Hindus called them as male diamonds.¹⁸ Tavernier visited the first mine Rammalakota which was situated in the region of the King of Bijapur in the Province of Carnatic. The original name was Raolconda, the proper form of the name Rammalakota means in Telugu ‘precious stone hill fort’. It had been identified about twenty miles south of Kurnool.¹⁹

Diamond mines in Ceded districts

Probably Hyene had only given more details of diamond mines of Rayalaseema. He recounted that the diamonds mines were found in the ceded districts, some in especially in the eastern and some in central divisions. Kadapa was the largest town in the Chennu Tlauk there two places namely Condapetta and Ovalumpally (probably Obulapuram), where diamonds occurred. On the Westside of this diamonds were mined at Lamdur and Pinchetgapadu besides near Gooty (Gutti) was exited several mines.²⁰ The diamonds mines near Kadapa were about seven miles north-east from the town, on both banks of the Pennar river. These mines were

within half a mile of the eastern range of hills, Far East from the river and Condapetta and on grounds belonging to a small village called Kanaperty. It was said the mines at Kadapa had been worked for several hundred years with various success and not long ago a large diamond was found which was stated full of flaws and weighed one and half pagoda or seventy grains. He further informed that the mines were in surrounding cultivated fields appeared heaps of stones and pits half filled with rubbish in the middle of which found a number of people at work in a new mine.²¹

Candapetta and Currapully

Hyene told that at Condapetta the miners worked for a long time past that it was nearly exhausted. They had not found diamonds of any considerable size. But they perceived many places in the neighbourhood potential and pointed out at close to the spot of Condapetta in which they were working and another place very extensive one near Currapully.²² The Ovalumpilly mines were about six miles from Kadapa on the west side of the river Pennar. It was of more recent discovery than the other mines and it was only forty years since they had been worked. As much as Hyene could learn from the miners the diamonds found in it were in the form of small flat or round pebbles and never occur crystallized. However they were said that diamonds were superior lustre and hardness and much better than those found further westward. He added that a few days after he had been there they found a diamond weighing fourteen carats estimated at about 200 pagodas value.²³

Diamonds mines at Banganapalle

Hyene informed that the diamond mines at Banganapalle was visited by him in 1808. It was probably forty or fifty miles from Kadapa. The bed in which the diamonds occurred at the place was a solid ground. He emphasised that to throw all the light in our power upon the nature of the beds in which the precious and rare production of nature had been found.²⁴ The labourers worked here in the less value of the diamonds mines, the lowest order of Hindus called chuoklers (perhaps tanners or locally known as *Madiga* one of the sub-caste in Schedule Caste) ‘from their occupation they are usually called hill people’ he told.²⁵ According to Hyene no place was more than one diamond bed found under the same but this bed frequently varies in its depth within a

very limited distance. To distinguish it near Kadapa it was within three or six feet of the surface, at Mallavilli and Partel or Ganipartala in the Masulipatam district, its depth was twenty feet whereas at Banaganapalle which varied from ten to twenty feet in a very small extent of ground.²⁶ ‘This Banganapalle bed or matrix was itself a detrital formation and possible the diamonds have come from an older rock’.²⁷

Vajra Karur mine

Tavernier informed that Currure known as Wajra-or Vajra-Karur, in the Guty Taluk of the Bellary District. It was confirmed that the statement was taken by Mir Jumla from the Hindu Rajas who gave the most famous and most ancient of all the mines with the Carnatic some years earlier. it was alleged that the diamonds up to ‘a seize (? ser) weight, which was equal to about 9 ounces troy, or 81½ pagodas, had been found there ; the mine was privately worked by the King, and the stones produced from it were large and well spread.’²⁸

Hindus distinguished diamonds with caste names

Methwold appended that in this country also much crystal and many other kinds of transparent sort stones had little value which were named as ‘garnets, amatists, topasses, aggats, and such like’.²⁹ But Hyene recognized and appended that here the names of diamonds were classified into four kinds according to their beauty, value and as connected them to the four fold caste system like “the Bramha diamond is described as of the colour of clear milk; the Chetra, of clear honey, the Vysea, of cream; and the Sudra, of a frog colour, or a smoky greyish white”.³⁰ It indicated that the Brahmin diamond most worth than others whereas the Kshtriya and the Vyshya diamonds were more price than Sudra diamond.

Diamonds cutting

Thevenot explained that when they found imperfection diamond would cut to take out some grain of sand and saw where it was to be cut. Then they laid it upon a hole which was in a piece of wood, they put on the iron lock there it was sawed and striking as smooth as might be cut through the diamond. In case of sapphire stone they cut with a ‘bow of wire’ where one workman handled the bow another continuously poured emery stone³¹ liquid solution upon stone

then they easily finished their work. Tavernier appended that at Rammalakota mine plentiful lapidaries (diamond- cutters) were there and everybody had a wheel (wood or steel) about the size of the plate. One stone on each wheel placed by them to the discovery of the position of the lines of cleavage and constantly poured the water on the wheel until they found the ‘grain’ of the stone. The ‘grain’ had been found poured on oil and not spared the dust of diamonds because it was also costly.³² He further informed that by nature some diamonds might be hard and in certain points of a stone to be exceptionally hard the Indian lapidaries would not hesitate to cut such a stone, the diamonds- cutters in Europe would be unwilling to undertake it. But the Indian lapidaries charged something extra for their trouble.³³ Hyene said that the merchants bought the diamonds which was carried to Madras where the larger diamonds was chiefly used in cutting and the large crystals might be cut into brilliant.³⁴ At last Hyene opined that Golconda was the repository of all large diamonds but in the neighbourhood of Golconda no diamond mines was to be found. The mines should be in the company’s territories because the Nabob had stipulated an exclusive right by treaty to them.³⁵

Destructive mode of mining opposed farmer or ryots

Hyene informed that during diamond searching in the bed very desultory and destructive mode of mining was followed and ‘they never employed gunpowder to blast the rock’. A man chose a piece of ground keep holes and open at top, sometimes indeed the work was carried on for some extent, if it was not fruitful he speedily left and proceeded to another ground. It was looked as a lottery. This method of proceeding, a great deal of ground was wasted and much money lost. The farmers or ryots were also strongly opposed to the extension of the diamond mines and averse their encroachments with all their influence because the plenty of cultivating ground went on vain.³⁶

Conclusion

The Diamonds are most valuable and commercial article of trade. The searching for Diamonds is most difficult job. Marco Polo explained the searching of diamonds upon the earth but the other travellers mentioned the mining process for diamonds under the earth. The travellers stated that natives used three types of searching methods for diamonds. Gani- Kollur,

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